

concentration ranging between 40 μg and 10 mg of the metal, at pH 5.3–6.8, can be satisfactorily titrated against EDTA using about 0.5 ml of 0.01M ANP_mD indicator solution. The titration can be performed between 20°–25°. The disappearance of the blue colour indicated the end-point. In reverse titrations, which can also be performed, the end-point was given by the appearance of blue colour.

Chelatometric determination of iron : To iron solution (metal concentration 40 μg –10 mg) add 2.0 ml of 1% hydroxylamine hydrochloride (to reduce any Fe³⁺ present to Fe²⁺), adjust pH between 5.3 and 6.8 by adding 10.0 ml of acetate buffer and add 0.5 ml of 0.1M ANP_mD indicator solution. Dilute the solution to about 25 ml. Titrate slowly while shaking with standard EDTA when the blue colour completely disappears.

Interferences : In determination of 2.7920 mg of iron(II), which corresponded to 5.00 ml of 0.01M EDTA solution, the presence of 500 mg each of Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, CNS⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₃²⁻, tartrate, thiourea, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Al³⁺, In³⁺, Tl⁺, Sc³⁺ or Hg²⁺ (masked with I⁻); 300 mg of F⁻, S₂O₃²⁻ or Sn²⁺; 250 mg of Mn²⁺; 200 mg of BO₃³⁻; 70 mg of Cu²⁺ (masked with thiourea) and 20–25 mg of C₂O₄²⁻, Zn²⁺ (masked with tartrate) or V⁴⁺ (masked with F⁻) did not interfere. However, CN⁻, IO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, citrate, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mo⁶⁺ and platinum-group metals should be absent.

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Studies on the Peptization of Oil-seeds of Saurashtra

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SEVERAL workers have extracted the nitrogenous constituents from oil free seeds, by means of various agents such as alkalis, acids and salt solutions. The process of extracting nitrogenous constituents from proteinaceous material is termed as peptization. This can throw light on the Indian method of cooking. During the cooking habits by how such nitrogen is peptized by addition of salt and other spices can be studied.

Smith *et al.*¹ extracted the nitrogenous matter from oil free soyabean meal by different acids and alkalis over a wide range of pH values. They also studied the protein for Alaska peas for peptization by various peptizing agents, at different pH. Fontaine *et al.*² studied the peptizability of the nitrogenous constituents of pea-nut meal.

Painter *et al.*³ studied the nitrogenous constituents of flaxseed and observed that salt solution dispersed between 43 to 81% of the nitrogen of finally ground oil free flaxseed meal.

Vasavada *et al.*⁴ studied the pulses of Gujarat for their peptization at different pH values. With different peptizing agents, Saxena *et al.*⁵ studied the vegetables and fruits of Saurashtra. They concluded that minimum dispersion of nitrogen is at 5.8 pH for proteins of Pomegranate and maximum dispersion of nitrogen at 12.2 pH of Tandalja with NaOH as a peptizing agent.

With the same background, few common oil-seeds of Saurashtra were taken for the study of peptization.

Some of the samples which have been selected are:—(1) Rapeseed; (2) Methiseed; (3) Groundnutseed; (4) Ajmaseed; (5) Sunflowerseed; (6) Tilseed (White variety); (7) Tilseed (Black variety); and (8) Tilseed (Red variety).

The results which have been recorded in the table have good correlation with the results of peptization worked out by other workers.

TABLE

Sr. No.	Oil-seeds	Minimum		Maximum	
		%	pH	%	pH
1.	Rapeseed	14.4	5.8	75.0	12.2
2.	Methiseed	19.0	5.8	85.5	12.2
3.	Groundnutseed	14.5	5.8	86.8	12.2
4.	Ajmaseed	9.5	5.8	89.1	12.2
5.	Sunflowerseed	5.7	5.8	81.0	12.2
6.	Tilseed (White Variety)	15.5	4.8	87.0	12.2
7.	Tilseed (Black Variety)	15.8	4.8	81.5	11.5
8.	Tilseed (Red Variety)	15.0	4.8	86.8	12.2

Experimental

Dry flour (4.0 g) were taken in an Erlenmeyer flask (250.0 ml) capacity. The peptizing agents were prepared from stock solution of acid, alkali and salt. The peptizing agent were added to the ground samples and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.5, 4.8, 5.8 and 7.0 for hydrochloric acid (0.06N) as the peptizing agent and at pH 7.0, 8.5, 9.5, 10.5, 11.5 and 12.2 for the sodium hydroxide (0.1N) as peptizing agent. The pH of mixture was adjusted at 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 4.0, 5.8, 7.0, 8.5, 9.5, 10.5 and 11.5, respectively for the sodium chloride (1.0N).

After the addition of the peptizing agent, the mixture was shaken mechanically for 1 hr and then centrifuged for about 15 min at 1400 r.p.m. The supernatant layer after centrifugation was collected and 25.0 ml of this aliquot portion was subjected to nitrogen estimation by the modified method of Peach and Tracey⁶.

The results of the peptized nitrogen estimated in term of percentage of the total nitrogen.

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Effect of Viscosity and Inorganic Nucleophiles on the Decomposition of 2-Methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide

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EARLIER we have presented¹ in detail the mechanism of hydrolysis of 2-methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (I) which is an useful intermediate for the preparation of mesoionic s-triazole systems². Despite numerous experimental data in favour of a neutral tetrahedral intermediate (II) at the rate controlling stage, there was no direct evidence against possible intervention by any hydrated complex, such as III, which could possibly arise via an encounter³ with the solvating species (water).

Moreover, some recent observation on cation-anion interaction^{4,5} also prompted us to examine more closely the effect of various inorganic nucleophiles on rate constants in order to identify the possible cause(s) of observed negative salt effect on I. It is in this context that additional experimental data are presented here in support of our previously proposed mechanism of hydrolysis of I.

Experimental

Materials: The substrate (I), m.p. 185-86°, and the inorganic salts (AR grade) were dried under vacuum and stored in a desiccator prior to their use. Methanol was purified as before⁶ and glycerol (AR) was used as such from fresh bottle. Stock solutions (2M) of the following salts in conductivity water were used for adjusting the ionic strength of the reaction medium: NaSCN, NaNO₃, Na₂SO₄, Na₂S₂O₃, KF, KCl, KBr, KI and KCN.

In glycerol-water system weighed quantities of glycerol and water were added to known weights of a stock solution of the substrate (I) in glycerol in order to control the glycerol content (% w/w) of the medium. But in the case of methanol-water system (50% v/v), aliquots of the stock solution (*ca* $1 \times 10^{-4}M$) were diluted with requisite volumes of methanol, water and the required salt solution in order to maintain the final ionic strength around unity ($\mu = 1.0$).

Kinetic measurements: In all cases kinetic runs were followed by spectrophotometric technique under neutral condition at $40 \pm 0.2^\circ$ by measuring the fall in absorbance at appropriate λ_{max} (Tables 1 & 2) determined previously through separate experiments. Other experimental details were the same as before^{1,6} and the necessary data are collected in Tables 1 & 2.

Results and Discussion

(a) *The effect of viscosity on rates:* Encounter limited rate constants³ are normally in the range of 10^9 sec^{-1} whereas our observed rate constants in 50% methanol or glycerol are in the range of 10^{-4} sec^{-1} . Nevertheless, it is quite possible to observe³ a small overall rate constant with an encounter limited rate determining step. In this context, rate constants were calculated from kinetic runs in a series of glycerol-water mixtures which form an ideal⁷ solvent for our purpose.

Inspection of data in Table 1 now clearly shows a slow and monotonic rise in rate constant with increasing viscosity or glycerol content of the medium

